

Magnetic and Ligand Field Spectral Studies on Iron(III), Ruthenium(III), Rhodium(III), Palladium(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with *N*-(α -Pyridyl)furfural-2-aldehyde Thiosemicarbazone and *N*-(α -Pyridyl)thiophene-2-aldehyde Thiosemicarbazone

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N-(α -Pyridyl)furfural-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (PFT) and *N*-(α -pyridyl)thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (PTT) form complexes of the type $[M(PFT/PTT)Cl_2]Cl$, (where $M(III)=Fe, Ru, Rh$), $[Pd(PFT/PTT)]X_2$ (where $X=Cl, CN$) and $[M(PFT/PTT)X_2]$ (where $M(II)=Co, Ni$; $X=NH_3, Cl, NO_2$). Magnetic and electronic spectral studies suggest octahedral geometry for the $Fe^{III}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II} complexes except for the Pd^{II} complexes which are square-planar. Mössbauer spectra of Fe^{III} complexes also reveal high-spin octahedral stereochemistry of the ligands around Mössbauer atom. Ir studies suggest tetradentate nature of the ligands (PFT/PTT) with pyridinic-N, thioketo-S, azomethine-N and (furfuryl-O/pyridinic-N) respectively as bonding sites.

IN view of the pharmacological importance of *d*-metal complexes with heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones¹, we report herein the synthesis and characterisation of *N*-(α -pyridyl)furfural-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (PFT) and *N*-(α -pyridyl)thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (PTT). Their complexes with $Fe^{III}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II} have been isolated and characterised by chemical analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, Mössbauer, electronic and infrared spectral studies in order to evaluate the stereochemistry of ligands around these metal ions.

Experimental

PFT ($C_{11}H_{10}N_4SO$) and PTT ($C_{11}H_{10}N_4S_2$) were prepared by mixing furfural-2-aldehyde/thiophene-2-aldehyde (0.1 mol) with a hot ethanolic solution (50 ml) of α -pyridylthiosemicarbazide² (0.1 mol) with stirring. The buff brown (PFT) and pale yellow (PTT) solids obtained were washed several times with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol. Both the tlc pure compounds were found sufficiently active against *Bacillusrecous*. Average zone of inhibition from ethanolic (200 μg ml^{-1}) solution of PFT and PTT were 13.95 and 12.38 mm respectively.

The ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) were recorded on TESLA-BS-467 spectrometer and chemical

shifts being downfields from TMS as internal reference. The NH proton is bonded to the unsaturated nuclei and therefore it appeared at the lowest field at δ 10.12 (PFT) and 9.98 ppm (PTT). Sharp doublets observed at δ 8.1 and 8.22 ppm (PFT) and 8.22 and 8.34 ppm (PTT) were assigned to heterocyclic pyridine ring protons. The methine proton attached to furan ring (in PFT) and pyridine ring (in PTT) appeared as singlet resonance at δ 2.5 and 2.34 ppm respectively.

Preparation of metal complexes: Ferric chloride hexahydrate (2.70 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was mixed successively with refluxing solution of ligand PFT (2.46 g, 0.01 mol) or PTT (2.62 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in the same solvent. Yellowish to dark brown reaction mixture obtained was refluxed for ~ 1 h. On cooling, the resulting brownish coloured solid was washed several times with acetone and dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} at room temperature. Complexes of the other metal ions with PFT and PTT were prepared and isolated in a similar way by following 1:1 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The cyano derivative of the Pd^{II} complex with PTT was prepared by mixing ethanolic solution of NaCN. For ammonio derivatives of the Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT, alcoholic ammonia (1:1) was mixed with the reaction mixture till brownish product appears (pH 8.1) and the reaction mixture was refluxed

further for ~ 2 h. For nitro derivatives of the Co^{II} complex with PTT, cobalt nitrate hexahydrate was used. Yields for these complexes were found in the range 55–65%. In all of these complexes, ionic chlorine was estimated by adding ethanolic solution of AgNO₃ to the weighed complex. A white curdy precipitate obtained was isolated and ionic chlorine content found was in good agreement with that calculated. The complexes were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in MeOH, DMF and DMSO. All the complexes were found to be tlc pure. Electrolytic conductance values for the complexes in 10⁻³M DMF, were found to be 15.73–23.71, 107.10–131.2 and 170.50–181.50 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, indicating non-electrolytic, uni-univalent and uni-divalent nature of the complexes respectively.

Chemicals of AnalaR grade were used. Elemental analysis, magnetic moment, ligand field and ir spectra of the complexes were recorded as described earlier². Mössbauer spectra of the Fe^{III} complexes were recorded on a ECI MBS-35 spectrometer (Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi) at 298 and 78 K, using constant acceleration, operating in a multiscalar mode with time-operated electrodynamic device and using ⁵⁷Co as source. Na₂[Fe(CN)₅NO].2H₂O was used as calibrant and liquid air for spectra at 78 K. Analytical data of the ligands and the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Iron(III) complexes: The Fe^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT, having the values of magnetic moment 5.91, 5.98 B.M. at 298 K. The isomer shift 0.36, 0.38 mms⁻¹ at 298 K and 0.43, 0.44 mms⁻¹ at 78 K, and quadrupole splitting 0.74, 0.75 mms⁻¹ at 298 K and 0.79, 0.78 mms⁻¹ at 78 K respectively, reveal⁴ high-spin octahedral stereochemistry around the Mössbauer atom. The lower values of isomer shift observed may be attributed⁵ to a decrease in the 4s-electron density on the iron nucleus, which is due to the decreased covalency in donor metal bonds. The absorption bands for the Fe^{III} complexes observed at 13 520, 17 200, 23 750, 28 170 and 37 800 cm⁻¹ (PFT complex) and 14 060, 19 650, 25 400, 30 500 and 42 000 cm⁻¹ (PTT complex) are tentatively assigned⁶ to (⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}) = 10Dq; ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{2g}; t_{2g}→π*; π→e_g and π→π* transitions respectively. The calculated⁷ values of B₂₂ (1 229, 1 278 cm⁻¹), β₂₂ (0.94, 0.98), F₂ (94.63, 91.42 kK), F₄ (61.94, 64.22 kK) and π→π* (3⁸.40, 41.84 kK) of the Fe^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, indicate high-spin octahedral stereochemistry. The increased values of Condon-Shortley repulsion parameters F₂ and F₄ in comparison to free-ion values of 80.93 and 50.27 kK respectively, may be due to expanded radial function of the d-electrons after complexation. The accuracy of the present assignments is also supported by the calculated values of π→π*, which are in good agreement with the observed values.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd	Colour	M.p. °C	Molar cond.* Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					S	Cl	Metal
1.	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ SO (PFT)	Buff	178	—	18.54 (18.01)	22.25 ^a (27.76) ^a	4.17 ^b (4.06) ^b
2	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ (PTT)	Pale yellow	159	—	24.62 (24.42)	21.05 ^a (21.37) ^a	3.72 ^b (3.82) ^b
3.	[Fe(PFT)Cl ₂]Cl	Reddish brown	173	115.2	8.46 (7.84)	26.35 (26.08)	18.93 (18.67)
4.	[Fe(PTT)Cl ₂]Cl	Light brown	156	107.5	14.61 (15.08)	25.27 (25.09)	13.95 (13.16)
5.	[Ru(PFT)Cl ₂]Cl	Dark violet	161	131.2	7.46 (7.05)	23.72 (23.47)	23.04 (22.28)
6.	[Ru(PTT)Cl ₂]Cl	Blackish violet	173	107.1	18.24 (13.61)	21.96 (22.64)	22.08 (21.62)
7.	[Rh(PFT)Cl ₂]Cl	Reddish brown	167	127.0	6.82 (7.03)	23.68 (23.88)	22.40 (22.60)
8.	[Rh(PTT)Cl ₂]Cl	Reddish yellow	171	112.4	13.22 (13.57)	22.12 (22.59)	22.17 (21.82)
9.	[Pd(PFT)Cl ₂]	Buff	154	181.5	7.94 (7.56)	16.42 (16.77)	25.76 (25.13)
10.	[Pd(PTT)(CN) ₂]	Greyish yellow	158	170.5	14.84 (15.22)	—	26.55 (25.31)
11.	[Ni(PFT)(NH ₃) ₂]	Brown	155	19.25	9.16 (9.44)	—	17.60 (17.33)
12.	[Ni(PTT)(NH ₃) ₂]	Brownish yellow	165	23.71	15.94 (15.65)	—	14.88 (14.19)
13.	[Co(PFT)Cl ₂]	Dark red	148	15.73	8.22 (8.51)	18.46 (18.88)	15.31 (15.69)
14.	[Co(PTT)(NO ₂) ₂]	Light brown	150	21.55	14.11 (14.88)	—	13.64 (13.25)

*In 10⁻³ M DMF. ^aN%. ^bH%.

Ruthenium(III) complexes : For the present Ru^{III} complexes, the absorption bands observed at 20 700 (with PFT) and 18 780 cm⁻¹ (with PTT) are assigned⁹ to ²T_{1g}→²A_{2g} transition. The two other bands observed at 16 500, 22 700 (with PFT) and 14 100, 21 200 cm⁻¹ (with PTT), if assigned⁹ to two spin-forbidden transitions, then the separation energy between them would correspond to 8*B*. The values of 10*Dq* are calculated from the relation (*Dq/B*)=5.1. The values of effective magnetic moment at 301 K (1.51, 1.54 B.M.), 10*Dq* (39 252, 41 437 cm⁻¹) and *B* (775.0, 812.5 cm⁻¹) of the Ru^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, correspond to octahedral geometry around Ru^{III} ion.

Rhodium(III) complexes : For the Rh^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT, the values of magnetic moment (0.30, 0.30 B.M.) and the absorption bands observed at 13 750, 21 780, 30 760, 41 480 cm⁻¹ (PFT complex) and 14 500, 22 300, 32 750, 44 200 cm⁻¹ (PTT complex) respectively, are assigned⁹ to spin-allowed transitions ¹A_{1g}→³T_{1g}; ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{1g} (ν₁); ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} (ν₂) respectively following (t_{2g})⁵ (e_g)¹ configuration. The fourth band beyond 40 000 cm⁻¹ is of charge transfer type, indicating octahedral stereochemistry around Rh^{III} ion with diamagnetic nature of the complexes.

$$\nu_1 = \Delta - 4B + 86(B)^2/\Delta \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_2 = \Delta + 12B + 2(B)^2/\Delta \quad (2)$$

$$B = 472 + 28q + 50(Z^* + 1) - 500/(Z^* + 1) \quad (3)$$

where, *q* is number of electrons in partly filled 4*d*-subshell in Ru^{III} ion. Following equations (1)–(3), the calculated values of ν₂/ν₁ (1.41, 1.46), *B* (561.2, 653.1 cm⁻¹), β (0.77, 0.90), 10*Dq* or Δ (22 838, 23 340 cm⁻¹), *F*₂ (1 646, 1 625 cm⁻¹), *F*₄ (1 027, 1 040 cm⁻¹), L.F.S.E. (27.38, 28.35 kcal mol⁻¹) and effective cationic charge *Z*^{*} (1.46, 2.22) for the Rh^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, suggest¹⁰ octahedral stereochemistry around Rh^{III} ion with diamagnetic nature of the complexes. The reduced values of *B* obtained in comparison to free-ion value (720 cm⁻¹), are associated to considerable orbital overlap with an increased covalency in the metal ligand σ-bond as well as reduced effective cationic charge (*Z*^{*}).

Palladium(II) complexes : For the Pd^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT, the values of effective magnetic moment 0.38, 0.35 B.M. at 302 K and absorption bands at 18 750, 21 000, 28 600, 35 250, 47 000 cm⁻¹ (PFT complex) and 18 900, 22 800, 29 650, 36 700, 47 250 cm⁻¹ (PTT complex) are assigned¹¹ to spin-allowed transitions, ¹A_{1g}→¹A_{1g}=(Δ₁-*C*); ¹A_{1g}→¹B_{1g}=(Δ₁+Δ₂+4*B*+*C*); ¹A_{1g}→¹E_g=Δ₁+Δ₂+Δ₃±(3*B*+*C*); ¹A_{1g}→¹A_{2u} a¹E_u and ¹A_{1g}→*b*.¹E_u respectively. The higher energy bands around 35 000 and 47 000 cm⁻¹ are attributed to intra-ligand charge transfer transitions. The calculated values of the ligand field parameters Δ₁ (22 250, 22 400 cm⁻¹), Δ₂ (4 250, 5 900 cm⁻¹), Δ₃ (7 100, 6 350 cm⁻¹) and L.F.S.E. (76.09, 76.61 kcal mol⁻¹) from the Pd^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, are attributed¹¹ to the square-planer geometry

around Pd^{II} ion with diamagnetic nature of the complexes.

Cobalt(II) complexes : For the Co^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT, the values of magnetic moment 5.07, 4.99 B.M. at 301 K and the three spin-allowed bands at 8 650, 18 620, 20 800 cm⁻¹ (PFT complex) and 9 750, 18 900, 21 550 cm⁻¹ (PTT complex) are tentatively assigned¹² to ⁴T_{1g}(*F*)→⁴T_{2g}(*F*) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(*F*)→⁴A_{2g}(*F*) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(*F*)→⁴T_{1g}(*P*) (ν₃) transitions respectively. The values of 10*Dq* (9 970, 9 150 cm⁻¹), *B* (898.0, 869.0 cm⁻¹), β (0.80, 0.77), ν₂/ν₁ (2.40, 2.21) and ν₃/ν₁ (2.15, 1.93) for the Co^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, suggest¹² tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry of the Co^{II} complexes.

Nickel(II) complexes : For the Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT, the values of magnetic moment 2.92, 3.02 B.M. at 301 K and three sharp bands at 9 750, 15 300, 26 950 (PFT complex) and 9 750, 15 500, 27 000 cm⁻¹ (PTT complex) are tentatively assigned⁴ to ³A_{2g}(*F*)→³T_{2g}(*F*) (ν₁); ³A_{2g}(*F*)→³T_{1g}(*F*) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}(*F*)→³T_{1g}(*P*) (ν₃) transitions respectively. In addition to these bands, a weak shoulder (12 300, 12 450 cm⁻¹) is also observed in the complexes which is assigned¹³ to the split component of ³T_{2g}. The reduced values of *B*_{2g} (892.8, 994.9 cm⁻¹) for the Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively (free ion value 1 040 cm⁻¹) suggest covalent character in the bonds. The ratio ν₂/ν₁ (1.56, 1.58) and ν₃/ν₂ (1.75, 1.74) observed for the Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, are greater than the usual range (~1.50, ~1.70) for octahedral complexes. The amount of splitting in ν₁ band is taken as a measure of the degree of distortion, i.e. (35/4)*Dt*. The probable assignments to split components¹³ can be ³B_{1g}→³E_g for 9 500 cm⁻¹ and ³B_{1g}→³B_{2g} for 12 000 cm⁻¹. The values of crystal field radial parameters, viz. *Dt* (291.4, 308.5 cm⁻¹), *Dq.z*² (650, 705 cm⁻¹), *Dq.xy* (1 200, 1 245 cm⁻¹), ratio of NSH (normalised spherical harmonic Hamiltonian) parameters *DT/DQ* (0.186, 0.176) and L.F.S.E. (33.34, 33.39 kcal mol⁻¹) for the present Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, reveal^{4,13} distorted octahedral stereochemistry for the Ni^{II} complexes.

Infrared spectra : The sharp absorption bands observed at 1 620 and 1 600 cm⁻¹ for the free ligands PFT and PTT respectively, can be attributed to ν_{C=N} of imine-N, which on coordination shifted towards higher wave number by 15–25 cm⁻¹, indicating⁶ involvement of imino-N in coordination. Pyridinic nitrogen metal bond implied due to blue-shift of sharp absorption bands, viz. 1 590, 1 560 (PFT) and 1 540, 1 500 cm⁻¹ (PTT) in free ligands, are assigned⁴ to symmetric and asymmetric (ν_{C=C}+ν_{C=N}) frequencies due to pyridine ring, while pyridine ring breathing modes observed at 1 085, 1 075 (PFT) and 1 085, 1 070 cm⁻¹ (PTT) show red-shift. On complexation, the sharp bands observed in the free ligands at 825, 810 (PFT) and 835, 820 cm⁻¹ (PTT) assigned⁴ to ν_{C=S} shifted to lower wave

number with reduced in intensity, indicating involvement of thioketo-S in coordination.

Strong bands observed at 610, 595 cm^{-1} (PFT) assigned¹⁴ to furan ring deformation modes, show 15–25 cm^{-1} red-shift on complexation, indicating metal-ligand bonding through furfuryl oxygen. The strong bands observed at 640, 572 and 490, 471 cm^{-1} (PTT) assigned¹⁴ to thiophene ring (C=C) out-of-plane and (C–S–C) in-plane bending modes respectively, also show 15–20 cm^{-1} red-shift, indicating thiophene-S involvement in coordination. In the Ni^{II} ammonio complexes, medium broad bands observed at 3 240, 3 190, 1 180 (PFT complex) and 3 280, 3 160, 1 215 cm^{-1} (PTT complex) are assigned to $\nu_{\text{a}}(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\delta_{\text{s}}(\text{HNE})$ respectively. The frequencies observed at 2 145 and 2 131 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{CN} of cyano group. In the Co^{II} nitrate complex with PTT, the medium bands observed at 1 525 and 1 285 cm^{-1} are assigned to monodentate $\nu_{\text{O}-\text{NO}_2}$.

In all of the complexes, the medium to weak bands in the far-ir region, viz. 550–520, 454–427, 370–365 and 325–307 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned⁴ to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{imine}-\text{N}}$, $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{thioketo}-\text{s}}$, $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{Cl}}$ and

$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{pyridinic}-\text{N}}$ respectively, suggesting tetradentate nature of the ligands PFT and PTT on complexation.

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